

	NAME	SYMBOL	GO BIOLOGICAL PROCESS (Flybase)
1	<i>SNF4/AMP-activated protein kinase gamma subunit</i>	<i>SNF4Agamma a</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
2	<i>Gigyf</i>	<i>Gyf</i>	regulation of autophagy inferred from genetic interaction with Atg1, Atg13
3	<i>Nitrogen permease regulator-like 3</i>	<i>Nprl3</i>	negative regulation of TOR signaling inferred from mutant phenotype
4	<i>multiple ankyrin repeats single KH domain</i>	<i>mask</i>	inferred from mutant phenotype inferred from genetic interaction with Atg18a
5	<i>AMP-activated protein kinase alpha subunit</i>	<i>AMPKalpha</i>	negative regulation of TOR signaling
6	<i>Protein modification; protein ubiquitination</i>	<i>hiw</i>	autophagy inferred from direct assay
7	<i>Acinus</i>	<i>Acn</i>	regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
8	<i>Autophagy-related 17</i>	<i>Atg17</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype inferred from genetic interaction with Atg1
9	<i>Autophagy-related 14</i>	<i>Atg14</i>	regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
10	<i>forkhead box, sub-group O</i>	<i>foxo</i>	regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
11	<i>straightjacket</i>	<i>stj</i>	autophagosome maturation inferred from mutant phenotype
12	<i>mauve</i>	<i>mv</i>	negative regulation of autophagosome size inferred from mutant phenotype
13	<i>Darkener of apricot</i>	<i>Doa</i>	positive regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
14	<i>similar</i>	<i>sima</i>	positive regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
15	<i>Ecdysone receptor</i>	<i>EcR</i>	regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
16	<i>Protein phosphatase 2A at 29B</i>	<i>Pp2A-29B</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
17	<i>Adaptor Protein complex 2, alpha subunit</i>	<i>AP-2alpha</i>	positive regulation of autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
18	<i>cacophony</i>	<i>cac</i>	autophagosome maturation inferred from mutant phenotype

19	<i>rolled</i>	<i>rl</i>	macroautophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
20	<i>spaghetti-squash activator</i>	<i>sqa</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
21	<i>Ubiquitin-63E</i>	<i>Ubi-p63E</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype
22	<i>widerborst</i>	<i>wdb</i>	autophagy inferred from mutant phenotype

Supplementary Table 1: List of Adar edited transcripts encoding proteins required for autophagy. Source: FlyBase.